

Effective Teaching and Learning of Economics at Secondary School Level in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State: Issues and Prospects

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Abstract

One of the foundational subjects in secondary education is economics education. In order to solve personal and societal issues, the teaching and learning of economics becomes essential to any nation that aspires to great in its economic base. The paper x-rays the issues and prospects of teaching economics in Zamfara state public secondary schools, Researchers used secondary data for this being a qualitative type research. Print and online publications were used to gather the secondary data which was further translated using reviewed related literatures. The issues face in effective teaching and learning of economics in Gusau educational zone, Zamfara state were identified as; insecurity, large class size, poor supervision, inadequate infrastructure, a lack of an active association for economics teachers, inadequate teaching and learning materials, low motivation of staff and students, negative attitudes of students towards the studying economics. The following prospects were identified to address these issues: increasing funding for the economics program, recruiting qualified economics teachers, providing instructional materials, providing infrastructure facilities for both economics teachers and students, establishment of effective program and policies for economics teachers' capacity development. The following suggestion were identified: Government should provide adequate security to protect the secondary schools in Gusau local government area and the state in general, the state government should employ more professional Economics teachers, to provide more infrastructural facilities for both Economics teachers and students, to ensure effective motivation of Economics teachers i.e. increasing their salary, economics teachers should form Economics Teachers' association, there should be effective supervision of the Economics teachers in all the public secondary schools across the state.

Keywords: Economics, teachers, teaching and learning, Secondary school, students.

Introduction

Education is a fundamental issue in any given society that is a key to social, economic, and political stability. Education is a crucial part of economic progress. Eyibe (2016) asserts that education is a cultural process. "Education has been adjudged an instrument for societal development and advancement of human knowledge for harmonious relationship and interactions with his environment," according to Onebunne, J. et al. (2020, 85). It is both a developmental and a cultural process. It is a cultural process since it involves the transmission and modification of cultural norms among students and adults who are exposed to education. The second reason it is a behavioral process is that it involves both adults and schoolchildren who are gaining from education. Thirdly, the progression from a lower to a greater degree of educational achievement makes it a developmental process. Therefore, it is a method for fostering an individual's growth so that he can function effectively and efficiently in the society of today and make positive contributions to its development. Education can also be thought of as a systematic process for an individual's personal and societal growth on all levels—physically, mentally, spiritually, and socially. The unemployment problems facing the country can be addressed through equipping the young people with skills that can lead to self-employment, the curriculum therefore should equip the learners with skills and more so entrepreneurial skills and this therefore indicate the importance of economic education in the school curriculum.

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Instructional materials and teaching equipment hinder students' performance in economics in Zamfara state. Therefore, Economics teachers in the state should make use of appropriate teaching aid in teaching economics. They should also teach students in a well conducive environment for effective learning and performance. With teaching equipment's students begin to develop the necessary skills in reasoning, attitudinal and practical skills to solve practical problems. Moreover, teachers should make them available while teaching economics to students. Teachers and students should learn how to motivate themselves. Teachers should motivate their students since motivation refers to the process by which behavior is mobilized and sustained in the interest of meeting individual needs in achieving organizational objectives. Teachers should use various motivation strategies like reinforcement, feedback and so on, various teaching methodology in teaching economics for effective performance. A motivated student cannot forget what is being taught in the classroom because it was meaningful and clear to him. Therefore, students need to be motivated in the classroom. Moreover, teachers and students should show positive interest in the teaching and learning of economics to enhance effective performance in the subject.

After graduating from a higher education institution, a person becomes certified as an Economics teacher if they have acquired the necessary skills, knowledge, and abilities to teach economics at educational institutions. Degree Finders (2020) defines an economics instructor as someone who disseminates knowledge about money, business, macroeconomics, microeconomics, technology, and personal finance. Lesson plans are developed, lectures are given, exams are given, student work is evaluated, and assistance is given to students as required. Either public or private secondary schools, colleges, or universities regularly employ economics teachers. The ability to teach in several social studies topics is a requirement in many schools for economics teachers. The person must register with the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) in order to be accepted as a qualified Economics instructor in Nigeria. The second requirement is that the person read. B.sc (ed) According to Asikhai (2010), secondary education is meant to be the cornerstone and foundation for obtaining higher knowledge in university institutions. It is both an investment and a tool that enables a nation to progress economically, socially, politically, technologically, scientifically, and culturally more quickly. The fact that today's secondary schools fall short of the expectations placed on them by their performance in external tests is regrettable. There have been public outcries over the persistently poor performance of secondary school students in public examinations. Nwokocho and Amadike (2015), submitted that one indicator for testing the educational process of a nation is the academic performance of students in schools. The performance of students in Economics for some years now have been reported by different researchers and even national dailies as below average in public examinations, Punch newspaper (September 27, 2008). Gbadamosi, and Jegede, (2015) also observed that many students largely record poor performance in the subject. For instance, the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) results in Economics between 2000 and 2012 revealed that, less than 50% of the students that sat for the examination obtained the required credit pass except 2006 and 2012. Udekaigbo, Onionwu and Mbionwu (2009) observed that the teaching and learning of Economics programme in majorities of Nigerian public Secondary Schools have been seriously frustrated in recent time.

This issue is ascribed to the difficulty of converting some economic notions and theories into visual, usable realities. The usage of instructional resources is allegedly lacking by teachers, and as a result, children are performing poorly academically, particularly on external exams. The teachers of economics have been blamed for the students' dismal performance on external tests. According to research, many Economics teachers in Nigeria's public secondary schools are struggling with a variety of issues that are affecting how well they function at their particular schools. The purpose of this study is to analyze the issues faced by Economics teachers and students in the public secondary schools in gusau local government area of Zamfara State.

Economics as a Secondary School Subject in Zamfara State.

Nigerian students took economics for the first time in 1967 as a topic in the West African School Certificate Exam. Since earning a school certificate required two years of study, economics may have been included to the secondary school curriculum in Nigeria significantly later than the majority of other secondary school subjects—in 1966—than most others. However, before becoming a secondary school subject, economics was a subject that private applicants may take in the General Certificate Examination. The fundamental issues with modern society's economy were acknowledged. Since 1967, when the West African School Certificate Examination included economics as a subject of study, both the number of institutions that offer it and the number of test-takers has grown dramatically. An illustration, In Nigeria, the West African School Certificate Examination included economics for the first time in 1967. Since obtaining a diploma For instance, it was 0.07% of the total number of applicants who took the exam in 1967, climbed to 12.56% in 1969, 17.16% in 1970, and reached 76.95% by 1976, exactly 10 years after it began (Noun, 2006). According to Gbemisola (2016), sustained research and significant innovations

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lead to ongoing changes in the Nigerian educational system. The 6-3-3-4 curriculum's multipurpose curriculum (NERC) is designed to meet a student's demands on an intellectual, social, material, and spiritual level, therefore catering to the "whole man" notion; that is, to provide for the intellectual, social, material and spiritual needs of a student through its multi-purpose curriculum (NERC, 2000; FME, 1989). With this mind, the secondary school curriculum is divided into three parts namely: (i) Core subjects or vacation subjects (ii) pre-vocational subjects and (iii) Elective subjects or non-vocational subjects. The core subjects such as Mathematics, English language, one Nigeria language among: Yoruba, Hausa and others like Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Agricultural Science, and Economics are basic intended to give students opportunity to offer Arts or Science subjects in higher education of learning in zamfara state and beyond.

The objectives of teaching Economics at senior secondary school:

1. **Allocation of resources:** To develop among students of zamfara state a favorable attitude towards conservation and wise use of the natural and available resources, and avoid misuse of the resources and wastage.
2. **Profit maximization:** To teach zamfara state students on how individual and corporate business owners can increase their profit margin using Economics principles to guide their business.
3. **Provision of basic tools:** To familiarize students in the state with the basic terminologies and elementary ideas of economics and acquire skills in interpreting simple statistical tools for analyzing economic issues and individuals in the state and government in general.
4. **Solutions to Economic problems:** To enable students to acquire knowledge for the practical solution of the economic problems of the society, such as zamfara state, Nigeria, developing countries and the world at large.
5. **Participation in government:** To foster and urge among students of zamfara state for effective participation in the task of economic reconstruction for the development of the state and country in at large.
6. **Consumption pattern:** To exposes the students to the various patterns of consuming commodities available in different localities in zamfara state.

Issues on teaching and learning of Economics in Zamfara state Public Secondary School

The successful teaching of Economics in Nigeria's public secondary schools is hampered by a number of issues. Teaching huge classes is one of these issues, along with bad staff development programs, poor supervision, inadequate infrastructure, a lack of an association for economics teachers, poor instructional materials, low motivation, and insecurity.

Teaching and learning of Economics in the face of Insecurity in Zamfara State

The menace of insecurity, armed banditry, human displacement and cattle rustling had virtually posed serious security challenges to Zamfara state and Nigeria at large. This, made scholars (Egwu, 2015 and Momale, 2015) to view it as criminal enterprises with the consequence for socio- economic, political, cultural and psychological spheres of (affected) society. As such made both teachers and students to be absent from schools and making their lives difficult. Insecurity is the first issue that zamfara state government needs to tackle in public secondary schools. Zamfara State has been struggling with insecurity issues since 2015. The militants and bandits have assaulted public secondary schools. About 10 public secondary schools were attacked between December 2020 and June 2021; during these attacks, instructors and students were slain, while some were taken hostage by the bandits for ulterior motives. Numerous teachers have died. The performance of teachers, particularly economists, is being hampered by these insecurity issues. The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) claims that since the insurgency began in Nigeria's northeast in 2009, Boko Haram has killed 2,300 instructors there, according to the Cable (2019).The first issue is security.

Inadequate Instructional Materials in Public secondary schools

Inadequate Economics instructional materials is another major problem facing the Economics teachers in majorities of the public secondary schools in Zamfara state. Things that help teaching and learning process to be more effective and efficient. Richardson, R. (2010), submitted that that economic teaching need concrete objects when teaching, for example if a topic like money is to be taught, the teacher needs to show the students the currency, both notes and coins and their demonstration, in order to retain the topic in their memory. Furthermore, a set goal may not be reached by the teacher if he fails to choose and correctly use appropriate resources in teaching, because there are some students who learn better when they see and touch and others learn more when they combine all the senses of learning, sight, touch, and even tasting and smelling. Mark, (2017) observed that despite the fact that instructional materials are essential tools that can make learning practical and

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knowledgeable, they are not readily available in the state secondary schools leading to low level in academic performance of learners in government examination.

Inadequate economics textbooks in public secondary school libraries

Unprofessionally published text books: Akpochato (2015) rightly of pointed out that non- availability of required economics text books, journals and magazine hamper the effective teaching and learning of economics at the secondary and tertiary level of education in Nigeria. He reiterated that text books that would aid effective discussion of economics concept are not in appreciable quantity. Teachers in economics are challenged to write and publish current materials to stem the gross inadequate of material in the area.

Low Motivation of teachers and students

Economics teachers are poorly motivated. The allowances and treatment given teachers in other subjects like mathematics, English language and sciences subject teachers are not given to the Economics teachers. Gbemisola (2016) observed in his study that on the part of Economics teachers' motivation, that 88.9% of the respondent agreed with the Economics teachers' lack of motivation. Motivation in terms of provision of a conducive staff room or office, teaching aids, skill acquisition and re- training on the; part of government and school authority have hindered their performance, which also indirectly affects the teaching and learning of economics in the zamfara state public schools.

Lack of adequately qualified Economics Teachers Association

Lack of Economics Teachers' Association is another problem facing the Economics teachers in Zamfara state Secondary schools. There is no any formal association in charge of professional development for Economics teachers even though the few once coming up are not strong enough to meet up the various challenges facing the Economics teachers. Noun (2015) submitted that all secondary school subjects which are regarded as established and important have associations for example; there are associations for subjects like English language, History, Geography and Sciences. Even the teachers of French in Nigeria are known to have only a few secondary school students yet they have an association.

Poor supervision

Many economics teachers are facing the problems of effective supervision due to shortage of professional Economics supervisors in the various Ministries and Agencies of government saddled with the responsibilities of supervising Economics instruction in the secondary schools are inadequate. Many Economics teachers are not constantly been supervised and even when supervised, non -economics supervisors are used for the supervision which is not encouraging due to different in teaching methodologies and approaches

Negative Attitudes of Students towards the Studying Economics

Economics teachers are also facing the problem of attracting students to study Economics in their various schools now. Economics is an elective programme in the Nigerian secondary schools. Students have many options. This make the students to avoid Economics even when chosen demonstrates some negative attitudes that is not encouraging the Economics teachers. Many students see Economics as voluminous and bore to read and study. They have negative mentality about the concept of the subject

Prospects in effective teaching and learning of economics in Zamfara state public secondary schools

1. The state government should collaborate with the federal government to provide adequate security to allow students go to school and study with peace.
2. The state government should provide more infrastructural facilities in all the Zamfara state public secondary schools.
3. It is important for the state ministry of education to encourage both students and teachers to study and teach economics by providing them with resources like high-quality textbooks and other study aids for the local government of Gusau and the state as a whole.
4. The state and federal governments should guarantee enough salary for teachers, fast and consistent payment of salaries, advancement, and better working conditions. The Zamfara state government ought to make sure that the state teachers are at least content with their pay, the minimum wage, and other perks related to their employment as instructors. Giving teachers scholarships to help them learn more about the subject would also produce positive results and should be done.

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5. Economics teachers in the state should form an association where issues concerning Economics programme can be discussed and ways of developing the programme suggested.
6. State ministry of Education should make sure that the economics education programme be supervised by the respective institutions in charge of Economics supervision.

Conclusion

Economics teachers are professionals employed to teach economics in Nigerian public Secondary Schools. It has been discovered that many economics are facing with challenges while implementing the economics programme their various schools. The paper identified teaching of large classes, poor supervision, inadequate infrastructural facilities, lack of Economics Teachers' Association, inadequate instructional materials, poor motivation and insecurity were identified as problems facing Economics teachers teaching in Zamfara state public secondary schools. In order to address these problems, the authors suggested that government should increase in the funding of Economics programme, employ more professional Economics teachers, provide more infrastructural facilities for both Economics teachers and students, motivate the Economics teachers, Economics teachers should form Economics Teachers' Association and effective supervision of the Economics teachers should be ensured in all public secondary school across the state.

Recommendations

1. Government should provide adequate security to protect the secondary schools in Gusau local government area and the state in general.
2. The state government should employ more professional Economics teachers.
3. To provide more Economics instructional materials for effective teaching and learning in the state.
4. To provide more infrastructural facilities for both Economics teachers and students.
5. To ensure effective motivation of Economics teachers i.e. increasing their salary.
6. Economics teachers should form Economics Teachers' Association.
7. There should be effective supervision of the Economics teachers in all the public secondary schools across the state.

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